

**Knowledge sharing and service innovativeness in offshore outsourced software
development firms**

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Abstract

Purpose- The purpose of the study is to investigate the effects of knowledge sharing on innovativeness in offshore outsourced software development firms.

Design/methodology/approach- For the study, survey methodology was used and 408 respondents attached to offshore outsourced software development firms in Sri Lanka responded. The hypothesized relationships were examined by structural equation modelling.

Findings- The analysis yielded two component factor structure for knowledge sharing, which were termed as knowledge sharing practices and knowledge availability. It was found that both knowledge sharing practices and knowledge availability significantly positively predict innovativeness. The study provided empirical data to support the contention that organizations should be able to timely deliver knowledge to the right user to enhance innovativeness.

Practical implications- The findings suggest the importance of creating an environment conducive for software developers to share information, insight, lessons learned, and effective practices. Further, organizations have to establish mechanisms to capture and capitalise knowledge residing in employees.

Originality/value- In the knowledge-intensive offshore business sectors such as software development, economic value is found more in intangibles and less in tangibles. The sharing of knowledge leads to the dissemination of innovative ideas, which could improve work processes and develop new business opportunities. Therefore, it is important to conduct research that would lead to better understand drivers that enhance the innovativeness of service offerings of firms located in developing countries when competing internationally in offshore outsourced software development.

Key words Knowledge management practices; Knowledge sharing practices; Innovativeness; Offshore outsourcing; Software development; Sri Lanka

Paper type Research paper

Introduction

Knowledge sharing is an organizational innovation, which leads to the dissemination of innovative ideas that has the potential to improve work processes and to develop new business opportunities (Lin, 2008; Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995; Yi, 2009). Although knowledge sharing is a natural function that takes place automatically, it could be very much controlled at the level of individuals (Staples and Jarvenpaa, 2001). Therefore, unless organizations facilitate the sharing of knowledge that employees use in their daily work activities, it is likely to lose knowledge once employees leave the organization (Gupta and Govindarajan, 2000; Lam, 2000). Further, even if individuals stay with the organization, the full extent of their knowledge may not be realized and utilized unless opportunities are provided for them to share the knowledge with others in the organization (Weiss, 1999). Therefore, voluntary sharing of knowledge in organizations has been identified as very important (Andrews and Delahaye, 2000; Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). The current study focused on the influence of knowledge sharing on innovativeness of offshore outsourced software development teams.

For several reasons, research into knowledge sharing in offshore outsourced software development is important. First, business firms from Western countries, especially, the USA, Canada, and the Europe offshore outsource software development to other countries with sufficient infrastructure and skilled human resources at a lower cost. These firms, which are mostly located in Asian developing countries, including Sri Lanka, have to learn how to satisfy these foreign client firms for sustained competitive advantage (Ueltschy et al., 2007). Hence, the literature emphasizes the importance of conducting research that would lead to better understand drivers that enhance firms' innovativeness of service offerings when competing internationally in offshore outsourced software development (Essén, 2009; Javalgi and Martin, 2007). Although previous studies have investigated different aspects of knowledge sharing in offshore software development such as the quality of cross-functional knowledge sharing (e.g. Ghobadi and D'Ambra, 2013) and team characteristics influencing knowledge sharing (e.g.,

MacCurtain et al., 2010), it is very rare to find previous empirical studies that investigated innovativeness and the effect of knowledge sharing on it in this context.

Second, in connection to the above, previous studies provide evidence that knowledge sharing in software development teams leads to superior team performance (Faraj and Sproull, 2000; Ghobadi and D'Ambra, 2013). However, the sharing of knowledge in team work settings succeed only if team members actively engage in knowledge sharing and by the efficient management of knowledge for the use by new teams with new projects (Berends et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2010). Further, one of the negative aspects associated with non-hierarchical work teams, such as software development, is team members' reluctance to share their knowledge with the others (Cabrera and Cabrera, 2005), which may have negative consequences for firms' competitive and international advantage (Javalgi and Martin, 2007).

Third, in the knowledge-intensive offshore business sectors such as software development, economic value is found more in intangibles and less in tangibles. However, on the one hand, knowledge and expertise that software developers possess leads to rapid obsolescence due to frequent technological advancements and their success is determined not just by what they know but by how fast they can learn and share their learning (Tymon and Stumpf, 2003). On the other hand, skills possessed by software developers remain highly marketable; they enjoy a considerable labour market power, with a high level of occupational identification, and they tend to move across organizations rather than thinking in terms of a long-term commitment to a single organization (see Scholarios and Marks, 2004). In addition, the use of project-based temporary work structures and associated temporary work processes making the length of stay of a software developer attached to a particular project is limited (Turner et al., 2008). In this context, for the sustainable growth knowledge sharing has become a key activity.

Finally, this sector possesses challenges for people management due to its people-intensive nature. The literature suggests that firms involved in outsourced work generally lack organizational resources that underpin the operation of an internal labour market (Walsh and

Deery, 2006). For instance, in the context of Indian offshore work, Raman et al. (2007) report that the hiring of new talent for this sector has become more expensive due to the shortage of appropriate skills while training a replacement has also become a critical problem due to high labour turnover rates in the sector. Therefore, when capturing and capitalizing on individual capabilities, a research addressing knowledge sharing in this sector is interesting, relevant and timely. Such an investigation holds a number of implications for research on people management in offshore outsourcing sector.

In the above context, the purpose of the study is to investigate the relationship between knowledge sharing and innovativeness in offshore outsourced software development firms. Drawing upon a random sample of software developers engaged in offshore outsourced software development firms operating in Sri Lanka the study specifically examined 1) knowledge sharing occurring in offshore outsourced software development firms, 2) effect of knowledge sharing on innovativeness of offshore outsourced software development firms, and 3) effect of demographic characteristics of individuals (i.e., age, gender, tenure, and level of education), and firm level contextual factors (i.e., firm size and years of industry presence) on innovativeness. Consistent with the objectives, the rest of the paper describes briefly the Sri Lankan context related to the study and reviews the literature relevant to the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on managerial implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

The Sri Lankan context

Advancements in information and telecommunications technologies made it easier and faster to outsource numerous services overseas spanning the entire value chain by taking the advantage of lower costs and broader talent pools around the world (World Bank, 2006). One of the fastest growing business sectors contributing to economic growth of Sri Lanka since the 1990s is information technology. Sri Lanka has become one of the promising investment destinations in

the Asia-Pacific region where offshore outsourced IT firms have been located (Flecker and Huws, 2003). In October 2013, Sri Lanka won the UK National Outsourcing Association's (NOA) Offshoring Destination of the Year (2013) Award confirming its status as a leading business process outsourcing destination (National Outsourcing Association, 2013).

Sri Lanka's offshore outsourcing sector had approximately a 50,000 member IT workforce by the end of 2009 (Sri Lanka ICT Association, 2010). In this regard, the World Bank (2006) states that although cost is an important factor in attracting offshore businesses, it is not the only criterion that clients consider in making site selection. In terms of labour quality and external labour market size, the World Bank (2006, p. 29) states "despite its small (labour force) size, the country (Sri Lanka) turns out a significant number of technically qualified individuals especially in IT, accounting and business management". Hence, the World Bank (2006, pp. 20-29) suggests that Sri Lanka's comparative advantage is in the quality and not in the quantity of its labour force.

As IT firms build on knowledge workers, absorbing and retaining suitable personnel is the focal point. The literature suggests challenges in attracting and retaining suitable personnel for this sector (Barrick and Zimmerman, 2009; Budhwar et al., 2006). Previous studies conducted in Sri Lanka too provide evidence for difficulties in attracting and retaining suitable personnel (e.g., LIRNEasia, 2006; Sri Lanka ICT Association, 2010), and suggests that IT firms tend to acquire individuals with required capabilities from the external labour market (Mahahettige, 2008) creating a high labour turnover in the sector (Wickramasinghe, 2009). The employee turnover rate in IT sector was 11% percent in the year 2009 (Sri Lanka ICT Association, 2010). Information technology firms adopt various poaching strategies to recruit IT personnel and the premium on industry experience is very high in compensation decisions (Mahahettige, 2008, Sanjeevani, 2009). Further, the employers' preference for job specific skills and experience creates an environment for IT personnel to hop from one workplace to another and maximise their future employability (Mahahettige, 2008; Wickramasinghe, 2009). This may give them a feeling that their experience is rewarded (Mahahettige, 2008). Hence, employees

may have a small number of years of experience in their present workplaces although they may have several years of service in the industry as a whole (Wickramasinghe, 2009). However, since firms expect new recruits to stay with them for about two years from the day they start (Sri Lanka ICT Association, 2007) firms do not expect long-term employee commitment from their IT professionals. As a result, training and development activities provided by the firms emphasise short-term productivity (Mahahettige, 2008). Yet, one could argue that IT professionals today have a much shorter cycle before their skills become obsolete (Edvinsson and Camp, 2005; Lee, 2002).

In this regard, the literature suggests that human resource issues prevailing in offshore software development across countries are not very much unique (e.g. Huckman et al., 2007; Raman et al., 2007). This is due to the fact that foreign clients use similar set of success factors in making offshore site selection decisions (Flecker and Huws, 2003; Ueltschy et al., 2007; World Bank, 2006). Accordingly, previous studies on offshore outsourced software development in India (e.g., Arun and Arun, 2002; D'Mello, 2006; D'Mello and Sahay, 2007; Huckman et al., 2007), knowledge intensive business sectors in India (Budhwar et al., 2006; Raman et al., 2007), software development in Scotland (e.g. Scholarios and Marks, 2004), Austria and Netherlands (e.g., Turner et al., 2008) also suggest the prevalence of similar human resources issues. Some of such frequently cited human resources issues in relation to software development personnel include high labour turnover (e.g., Budhwar et al., 2006; Raman et al., 2007), lack of promotion opportunities (e.g., Scholarios and Marks, 2004), rapid skill obsolescence (e.g., Tymon and Stumpf, 2003), mobility (e.g., Huckman et al., 2007; Scholarios and Marks, 2004), and lack of long-term commitment to a single organization (e.g., Scholarios and Marks, 2004; Turner et al., 2008).

In this context, whether knowledge sharing is happening in offshore outsourced software development, whether knowledge sharing contributes to the innovativeness, and whether demographic characteristics of software developers (i.e., age, gender, tenure, and level of education), and firm level contextual factors (i.e., firm size and years of industry presence)

influence innovativeness are important questions worthy of empirical investigation to make global conclusions and informed decisions in enhancing innovativeness in a highly competitive environment.

Review of literature

Knowledge sharing

Knowledge sharing is the act of knowledge provider making knowledge available to others within the organization (Ipe, 2003; Mooradian et al., 2006; Szulanski, 1996). However, the literature on conceptualizing the term knowledge sharing is mixed (Szulanski, 1996; Van den Hooff and Van Weenen, 2004). For instance, Van den Hooff and Van Weenen (2004) stated that knowledge sharing includes both giving (transmission) and receiving (absorption) of knowledge. Wilkesmann and Wilkesmann (2011) also argued that providing and obtaining knowledge as different directions of knowledge transfer. However, Szulanski (1996) stated that knowledge sharing is not a two-way knowledge exchange between knowledge providers and knowledge recipients and knowledge sharing is limited only to the behaviour of knowledge providers. Teng and Song (2011) suggested that knowledge sharing can be either solicited or voluntary, where solicited knowledge sharing is referred to the sending and receiving of requests for knowledge, as well as the subsequent fulfillment of these requests while voluntary knowledge sharing is referred to the sending of knowledge without any prior solicitation. However, Davenport (1997) identified knowledge sharing as a voluntary act, where the term knowledge sharing implies that provider voluntarily presents knowledge in a form that can be used by others and it involves some conscious action on the part of the provider who possesses the knowledge and actively participates in the sharing process even though there is no compulsion to do so. Following the arguments made by Davenport (1997), in the current study the term knowledge sharing is used to refer to the voluntary provision of knowledge by those who possesses the knowledge to other members in the team.

Lowendahl et al. (2001) identified three types of knowledge that individuals share, namely know-how, know-what, and dispositional knowledge. According to Lowendahl et al. (2001) know-how includes experienced-based knowledge that is subjective in nature, know-what includes task-related knowledge that is objective in nature, and dispositional knowledge includes an individual's talents, aptitude, and abilities. Leinonen and Bluemink (2008) found that team members evaluate what knowledge is shared between them. According to Leinonen and Bluemink (2008) distributed team members' presumed shared knowledge did not focus directly the content of the shared project task. Instead, they suggest that distributed team members' presumed shared knowledge focus on how collaborative the distributed working processes are and what is the common goal. Further, Leinonen and Bluemink (2008) suggest that in order to construct new knowledge collaboratively the distributed team members have to explain their shared common frame of reference to coordinate their work. Hence, for the successful sharing of knowledge, interaction and communication among team members is vital (Cohen and Bailey, 1997). The literature identifies the importance of knowledge acquisition, information sharing, and the minimization of communication breakdown in software development since distributed software development projects involve diverse expertise drawn from various nationalities, functional units, etc (Andres and Zmud, 2002; Fang and Neufeld, 2009; Joshi et al., 2007; He et al., 2007). For instance, Faraj and Sproull (2000, p. 1554), in the context of software development, suggest the importance of coordination of expertise about who knows what in the team by stating that "teams must be able to manage their skills and knowledge interdependencies effectively through expertise coordination, which entails knowing where expertise is located, knowing where expertise is needed, and bringing needed expertise to bear". However, previous research provides evidence that cross-functional software development teams encounter several challenges in knowledge sharing (Espinosa et al., 2007; Joshi et al., 2007). For instance, Van der Bij et al., (2003) and Jarvenpaa and Staples (2001) suggest that since knowledge is a source of competitive advantage team members may hoard

knowledge or share knowledge that is incomplete. The current study investigates to what extent knowledge sharing is happening in offshore outsourced software development firms.

Previous empirical studies on knowledge sharing operationalized the term knowledge sharing in different ways. For example, Liebowitz (2002) provides evidence for the use of several measures such as counting the number of hits on personal postings, the number of documents submitted, the number of contributions to meetings, the number of written reports, the rate of contribution to knowledge databases, the number of new ideas, the number of improvement suggestions made, and the number of presentations made to explain an individual's sharing of knowledge. In this regard, although computer-based knowledge sharing is relatively easier to track, other forms of knowledge sharing which take place through informal conversations and personal networks, are difficult to monitor but may have a considerable impact on organizational performance (Yi, 2009). To overcome this difficulty, some researchers tried to quantify knowledge sharing by asking employees how often they shared work experience, expertise from education and training, and business knowledge obtained informally from others in the team (Lee, 2001). However, scholars (such as Yi, 2009) argue that such a listing and rating of knowledge dimensions do not constitute different knowledge sharing behaviours. In line with these arguments, several researchers attempted to measure knowledge sharing behaviour by inquiring individuals how frequently or how well they share knowledge with other members (Faraj and Sproull, 2000; Yi, 2009; Zárraga and Bonache, 2003). Some other researchers attempted to measure individuals' willingness or intention to share knowledge (Bock et al., 2005; Reyshav and Weisberg, 2010) by operationalizing the intention of knowledge sharing as the degree of one's positive feeling about sharing one's knowledge. In this regard, Choi et al. (2008) empirically investigated the relationship between knowledge sharing intention and knowledge sharing behaviour and reported a strong positive association between knowledge sharing intention and behaviour. In investigating the level of knowledge sharing in offshore outsourced software development, the current study operationalized the term

knowledge sharing in terms of how frequently and how well individuals share knowledge with other team members.

With regard to the relationship between individual characteristics and knowledge sharing, MacCurtain et al. (2010) argued that diversity in tenure in teams may lead to increased creativity and innovation; enhance the creation of new knowledge; and newcomers can add fresh perspectives and objectivity for the team. Accordingly, although MacCurtain et al. (2010) predicted that diversity in tenure will facilitate debate, reflexivity and knowledge sharing, their hypothesis was not supported by their survey findings. Wilkesmann and Wilkesmann (2011) argued that obtaining and providing knowledge will be represented by the interplay between experts and novices. Based on a case study, Wilkesmann and Wilkesmann (2011) found that both novices and experts need organizational leeway which allows time for providing and obtaining knowledge.

Knowledge sharing and innovativeness

The term innovation gives different meaning to different scholars (e.g. Calantone et al., 2002; Thompson, 1965; West and Farr, 1990). For instance, according to Calantone et al. (2002, p. 512), innovation implies “the generation, acceptance, and implementation of new ideas, processes, products, or services”. Thompson (1965) identified innovation as the generation, acceptance and implementation of new ideas, processes, products or services. According to West and Farr (1990) innovation is intentional introduction and the application of new products, processes, procedures, or ideas that are designed to significantly benefit the individual, group, organization or wider society. Some scholars suggest that innovation can be achieved through invention and exploitation (Kikoski and Kikoski, 2004; Roberts, 1987; Tushman and O’Reilly, 1996; March, 1991), where invention involves the search for new things while exploitation is making use of existing opportunities.

Fitzgerald et al. (1991) identified innovativeness in relation to the performance of innovation process and performance of individual innovations. According to Gallouj (2002),

product and process innovations are very much interrelated; the term “product” is often used to describe a process. Further, although innovation is almost always associated with technology, non-technological innovation can also be crucial. For instance, on the one hand, Rayna and Striukova (2009) suggest that finding new ways of thinking and offering a service or a product are particularly important in industries such as hotels where technological advances only result in limited improvements in the manner in which the business is conducted. On the other hand, Calantone et al. (2002) suggested that firms can enhance innovation capabilities by having state-of-the-art technology and using that technology in innovations, by having knowledge and ability to understand and anticipate customer needs, and by having an organization’s commitment to learning. Hence, innovativeness could be analyzed by industry or even by sector in terms of both technological and non-technological perspectives.

With regard to the relationship between knowledge sharing and innovativeness, both theoretical and empirical literature recognize the importance of knowledge sharing in supporting innovativeness (Finnegan and Willcocks, 2006; Hallin and Marnburg, 2008; Mohamed et al., 2004). For instance, Cohen and Levinthal (1990) state that interaction among individuals with different knowledge improves organizations’ ability to innovate. Kamaşak and Bulutlar (2010) argued that knowledge sharing is essential for both invention and exploitation nature of innovations. Further, Hargadon and Sutton (1997) argued that knowledge sharing among team members and also among groups within an organization may result in potentially new products or services. Furthermore, Ipe (2003) and Chang et al. (2007) identified knowledge sharing as a fundamental step in organizational knowledge creation process, and failures in effective knowledge sharing can constitute a serious barrier for this process, and as a consequence, for innovation effectiveness. With regard to empirical evidence for the relationship between knowledge sharing and innovativeness, several empirical studies provide evidence for a positive relationship between knowledge sharing and innovativeness (e.g. Camelo-Ordaz et al., 2011; Hu et al., 2009; Kamaşak and Bulutlar, 2010; Storey and Kelly, 2002; Brachos et al., 2007; Seidler-de Alwis and Hartmann, 2008; Swan et al., 2007). For instance, Storey and Kelly (2002)

identified the lack of knowledge as the main barrier to innovation in service firms. Swan et al. (2007) found a positive relationship between knowledge sharing and innovation in research and development projects. Further, den Hertog (2000) provided evidence that experience sharing supports innovation. Furthermore, Hong et al. (2004) found a significant positive relationship between knowledge sharing and new product development (Liao et al., 2007). The specific literature on software development teams also provides evidence that knowledge sharing leads to achieve innovativeness (e.g. Levina, 2005). With regard to specific literature on knowledge sharing in outsourcing firms, Lee (2001) provides evidence that knowledge sharing is one of the major predictors for outsourcing success. Based on the literature reviewed above, it is questioned in the current study whether the extent of knowledge shared by software developers with other team members influence innovativeness. Therefore, it is hypothesised for the study:

H1: Innovativeness will be significantly predicted by the extent to which knowledge is shared among individuals.

Demographics of the individuals and firm level contextual factors and innovativeness

The literature suggests that innovativeness can be influenced by individuals' demographic characteristics such as age, gender, tenure and the level of education (e.g. Hu et al., 2009). The literature further suggests that firm level contextual factors such as firm size, and the years of industry presence can influence firm innovativeness (Zhou and Li, 2012). For instance, Hu et al. (2009) found that gender significantly predicts employees' innovative behaviour. Further Zhou and Li (2012) found that firm size (as the logarithm of the number of employees) predicts the degree of technological advances in radical innovation ($p < 0.10$). Although it is rare to find empirical studies that investigated the influence of individual demographic characteristics and firm level contextual factors on innovativeness in software development projects, building on the prior research reviewed above the current study examined the effect of two firm level contextual factors (i.e., firm size and the years of industry presence) and four individual demographic

characteristics (i.e., age, gender, tenure, and the level of education) on innovativeness. Therefore, it is hypothesised for the study:

H2: Innovativeness will be significantly predicted by each of the demographic characteristic of individuals (i.e., age, gender, tenure, and the level of education) and firm level contextual factors (i.e., firm size and the years of industry presence).

Consistent with the literature reviewed above that suggests age (e.g. Hu et al., 2009), gender (e.g. Hu et al., 2009), tenure (e.g. Hu et al., 2009), the level of education (e.g. Hu et al., 2009), firm size (e.g., Zhou and Li, 2012), and the years of industry presence (e.g., Zhou and Li, 2012) may predict innovativeness, the above second hypothesis (H2) could be split into following sub-hypotheses:

H2.1: Innovativeness will be significantly predicted by the age of employees

H2.2: Innovativeness will be significantly predicted by the gender of employees

H2.3: Innovativeness will be significantly predicted by the firm tenure of employees

H2.4: Innovativeness will be significantly predicted by the level of education of employees

H2.5: Innovativeness will be significantly predicted by firm size

H2.6: Innovativeness will be significantly predicted by the years of industry presence of the firm

Methodology

Sample

The list of offshore outsourced software development firms was obtained from the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI), which is the government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating export-oriented business operations in the country through both foreign and local investments. It is compulsory by BOI Act (No.4 of 1978) that all the BOI registered firms should export at least 90% of their output. There were about 45 firms with more

than five years of industry presence and these were considered as the population of the study. A contact person was identified at each firm covering the entire population of the firms to distribute the survey questionnaire. Contact persons together with the author of this article randomly identified software developers, whose main job function is development and maintenance of a software product and employed fulltime in the present workplace during the last three years to distribute the self-administered survey questionnaire. A total of 408 usable responses resulted in 56% response rate. With regard to the demographic characteristics of respondents, 62% were male and 38% were female. All the respondents belonged to the age range of 24 to 37 years. 67% of the respondents had Bachelor's degrees or equivalent qualifications and 31% had postgraduate degrees as the highest level of education. The mean tenure in the present workplace was three and half years (S.D. = 1.03).

Measures, methods of data collection and data analysis

Knowledge sharing was measured by the four-item scale of Faraj and Sproull (2000) together with six items developed for the study in the Sri Lankan context. Faraj and Sproull (2000) developed and used this scale for a study on software development project teams, which is the context of the current study. To get more depth into knowledge sharing in the Sri Lankan context, six more items were added. Responses were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree (for item measures, refer to Table 1). Innovativeness was measured by the six-item scale of Calantone et al. (2002). This scale was chosen since they had conceptualized innovativeness as a behavioral variable in terms of the rate of adoption of innovations by the firm as well as an organization's willingness to change. Responses were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) very low to (5) very high (for item measures, refer to Table 2). Data on two firm characteristics (i.e., firm size and the years of industry presence) and four individual characteristics (i.e., age, gender, tenure, and the level of education) were also gathered for the analysis. Firm size was assessed by the number of full-time employees in the organization. Industry presence was assessed by the number of years that the firm is in

business operation. Age and firm tenure were measured in years. Gender (0 = female and 1 = male) and the highest level of educational qualification (0 = Bachelor's degree or equivalent and 1 = Postgraduate degree) were binary coded. The values for age, the years of experience in the present workplace, the number of employees in the firm and the years of industry presence were log transformed.

Considering the literacy of the respondents and the amenability of research questions, the self-administered survey questionnaire was in the English language. The questionnaire was pre-tested with a random sample that fitted with the intended sample of the study prior to the distribution.

For all measurement scales, standardized Cronbach's alpha was examined and principal component factor analysis (varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7. The study relied on self-reported data. However there are three central problems with subjective measures: positive response bias, the use of general single-item measures, and the level of information possessed by the respondent. To overcome the first problem, factor analysis was used following recommended procedure by Hair et al. (2006). To overcome the second problem, multiple item measures were used. To overcome the third problem, as suggested by Guest (2001) more than one respondent (N=408) was used. Further, procedural and statistical measures were taken to reduce common method bias in the current study. First, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension (a procedure recommended by Podsakoff et al. 2003). Second, factor analysis was used to conduct Harman's single-factor test; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff et al. (2003).

With regard to methods used for data analysis, descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation), correlation analysis and path analysis were used. For the path analysis, structural equation modelling (SEM) with maximum likelihood estimation was performed using AMOS 16.

Results and discussion

To identify the nature of knowledge sharing, following procedure was used. First, the 9-item measure was subjected to reliability analysis. The 9-item measure had a Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.789. Second, in the attempt to identify the underlying dimensions as perceived by respondents, exploratory factor analysis was conducted. Therefore, in the study, factor analysis (with Varimax rotation) was used as a data reduction technique to identify factors that underlie 9-items to be used in the subsequent analysis. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues should be greater than 1; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be 0.7. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test statistics were calculated. The KMO statistic was above the customary reference point of 0.5 for a satisfactory factor analysis to be proceeded. Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant – associated probability was less than the customary reference point of 0.05 for a satisfactory factor analysis to be proceeded. Table 1 summarises the results of factor analysis. Factor analysis yielded a set of two factors, which explained 74% of the variance. Factor 1 was labelled as “knowledge sharing practices”, and Factor 2 as “knowledge availability. The summary of results is provided in Table 1.

Take in Table 1

Same procedure was used to identify underlying factors of innovativeness. The 6-item measure had Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.774 and exploratory factor analysis yielded one factor, which explained 75% of the variance. The summary of results is provided in Table 2.

Take in Table 2

Means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations between the variables are shown in Table 3. As can be seen in Table 3, correlations between the two factors of knowledge sharing and innovativeness are positive and significant. Correlation analysis revealed that correlations between knowledge sharing practices and knowledge availability are low suggesting low collinearity while correlations between both knowledge sharing practices and knowledge availability and innovativeness are high suggesting better prediction in the subsequent analysis. As can be seen in Table 3, correlations between each the variables of age, gender, the level of education, tenure, the years of business existence of the firm and the number of employees in the firm and knowledge sharing practices and knowledge availability are not significant. In this regard, Kimble et al. (2010) did not find any significant relationships between employees' knowledge sharing intention and individual demographic variables of gender, age, education, and team tenure. Although MacCurtain et al. (2010) found that age diversity negatively influences knowledge sharing; they did not find significant relationship between tenure diversity and employees' knowledge sharing motivation.

Take in Table 3

In the stage 1 of the data analysis all variables were entered into the model. As predicted in H1, knowledge sharing, in terms of knowledge sharing practices and knowledge availability, significantly positively predicted innovativeness. This supports H1. However, as can be seen in Table 4, none of the individual demographic characteristics or firm level contextual factors was significant. Hence, all six sub-hypotheses relating to demographic characteristics (H2.1 to H2.4)

and firm level contextual factors (H2.5 and H2.6), and as a consequence their main hypothesis H2 are not supported in the current study.

Take in Table 4

To purify the SEM model, in the stage 2 of the data analysis, non-significant individual demographic variables and firm level contextual factors were removed from the SEM model (refer to Kremelberg, 2011). Fit measures of Chi-square, GFI, CFI, and RMSEA were used to evaluate the structural model. The final structural model achieved a good level of fit having a Chi-square = 98.57, CMIN/df = 2.78, CFI = 0.856 and RMSEA = 0.051. The summary of SEM results is provided in Table 5. As can be seen from Table 5, both knowledge sharing practices and knowledge availability have positive and significant relationship with innovativeness supporting H1. Squared multiple correlation of .373 suggests that both knowledge sharing practices and knowledge availability account for 37% of the variation of innovativeness.

Take in Table 4

Conclusions and implications

The study investigated the effect of knowledge sharing on innovativeness in offshore outsourced software development firms. For the study, software developers attached to offshore outsourced software development operating in Sri Lanka responded. The analysis yielded two component factor structure for knowledge sharing, which were termed as knowledge sharing practices and knowledge availability. It was found that both knowledge sharing practices and knowledge availability significantly positively predict innovativeness. Therefore, the findings support previous studies that suggested knowledge sharing creates positive results in innovativeness (e.g. Chang et al., 2007; Hargadon and Sutton, 1997; Ipe, 2003; Kamaşak and

Bulutlar, 2010). The findings also support previous studies that suggested positive influence of knowledge sharing in software firms (e.g. Levina, 2005) and offshore firms (e.g. Lee, 2001). Further, the study provided empirical data to support the claim (e.g., Hsu et al., 2007) that organizations should be able to timely deliver knowledge to the right user for enhanced organizational performance.

The study also investigated whether individual demographic characteristics (i.e., age, gender, tenure, and the level of education) and firm level contextual factors (i.e., firm size and the years of industry presence) predict innovativeness. The results of the analysis revealed that none of the individual demographic characteristics or firm level contextual factors was significant in predicting innovativeness. However, it is very rare to find previous empirical studies that specifically investigated the effect of individual demographic characteristics and firm level contextual factors on innovativeness in any research context. Hence, this is an area worthy of more future research. The findings suggested that correlation between each the variables of age, gender, the level of education, tenure, the years of industry presence and the number of employees and the level of knowledge sharing are not significant. Several previous studies (such as Kimble et al., 2010 and MacCurtain et al., 2010) also provide evidence for non-significant relationships between individuals' gender, age, education, and tenure and knowledge sharing in different country and work contexts.

The findings of the study have both theoretical and practical implications. With regard to the contribution of the study for research, there is surprisingly little empirical research specifically addressing the effect of knowledge sharing on innovativeness of services offshore outsourcing sector. Therefore, the findings of the study make a contribution to the literature by examining relationships between knowledge sharing and innovativeness, and contribution of individual demographic characteristics and firm level contextual factors on innovativeness. Therefore, the findings of this study provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area. The study not only utilised already existing measures to operationalize knowledge sharing but also created a set items, which led to identify

as knowledge availability. Future research could use this item measure to reproduce the measurement. In this regard, more empirical studies covering several organizations and country contexts are needed to provide information to make global conclusions and informed decisions in enhancing innovativeness in a highly competitive environment.

With regard to the contribution of the study for the practice, the results imply that team processes result in better sharing of knowledge which would lead to better team performance. According to van Vliet (2010, p. 2) in the software development there is an inherent tension between top-down development guidance through specifications and other means, and a bottom-up development and delivery of new features. As clearly stated in the literature (such as Liao et al., 2007; van Vliet, 2010; Wang and Wang, 2012; Zhi-guo and I-Jian, 2012), software development requires a huge amount of knowledge to be shared between several people involved in the development process such as architects and developers, testers and developers, configuration managers and integration testers for successful delivery of products/services; most importantly, this knowledge mainly remains tacit. On the one hand, if there are limitations to knowledge availability in the software development process, it will negatively influence in getting cross-functional work completed in timely and effective manner. On the other hand, based on the arguments of the resource-based view of the firm, knowledge can be considered as one of the most strategically important resource that organizations have. The findings of the study imply that the knowledge can be transformed into value, which would in turn lead to competitive advantage, through sharing of knowledge between and among software developers and having systems to manage the shared knowledge. Therefore, the findings suggest the importance of creating an environment conducive for software developers to share information, insights, lessons learned, and effective practices. Further, organizations have to establish mechanisms to capture and capitalise knowledge residing in employees. Therefore, it is important to establish systems and processes that can collect and store information and make it available for effective decision making. As stated by Bassi and McMurrer (2005), organizations that capture, apply and re-use knowledge and best practices among departments and divisions,

and have successful collaborative team structures are best able to leverage their knowledge and talent for business results. However, for the sustainable sharing of knowledge, firms may need to introduce mechanisms (such as reward and recognition) that encourage and recognize employees for their contribution to knowledge sharing.

Finally, it should be noted that this research was designed as a cross-sectional study employing survey methodology; the study relied on self-reported data. Future research studies in different samples that compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data are necessary to validate the links proposed in this study. In such studies, questionnaire survey may provide access to breadth of experience while the interviews may provide depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey.

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Tables

Table 1. Summarised results: factor analysis – Knowledge sharing

	Factor loading	
	Knowledge sharing practices	Knowledge availability
There is an exchange of information, knowledge, or sharing of skills among members	.802	
People in our team share their special knowledge and expertise with one another	.732	
More knowledgeable team members freely provide other members with hard-to-find knowledge or specialized skills	.796	
If someone in our team has some special knowledge about how to perform the team task, he or she tell the other members about it	.759	
My organization has effective systems in place to collect, store, and to share information among employees.		.862
My organization is very good at encouraging and enabling effective teamwork.		.831
My organization continuously reviews and updates its best practices.		.784
My organization provides employees with resources (including time) needed to promote knowledge sharing.		.763
We make better utilization of existing knowledge within a team to make thoughtful decisions at work.		.749
In my organization, employees trust their team members to get the job done.		.711
Explained variation	44.75	28.93
Eigenvalue	3.44	1.87
Cronbach's alpha	.801	.745

Table 2. Summarised results: factor analysis – innovativeness

	Factor loading
My organization frequently tries out new ideas.	.856
My organization is creative in its method of operation.	.848
Innovation in my organization is perceived as too risky and is resisted (r).	.824
My organization is often the first to market with new products and services.	.795
My organization seeks out new ways to do things.	.792
Our new product introduction has increased over the last five years.	.731
Explained variation	74.86
Eigenvalue	3.62
Cronbach's alpha	.774

r= reverse coded

Table 3. Correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	6	7	8	9
1 Age ^b	4.26	.44	1							
2 Gender ^a	.54	.50	.054	1						
3 Education ^a	.21	.41	.242*	.177	1					
4 Tenure ^b	4.00	1.18	.403**	.089	.231*	1				
6 Industry presence ^b	5.39	1.49	.260*	.028	.084	.087	1			
7 No. of employees ^b	6.25	1.43	.226*	.153	.170	.207*	.538**	1		
8 Knowledge sharing practices	3.68	.54	.003	.030	.145	.138	.052	.074	1	
9 Knowledge availability	3.59	.85	.078	.171	.159	.060	.319**	.368**	.211*	1
10 Innovativeness	3.52	.71	.032	.064	.217*	.050	.133	.186	.480**	.347**

Notes: ** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), * significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

^a Binary-coded variables. ^b Log transformed

Table 4. Summarised results: preliminary analysis

Path	Standardized regression estimate (significance)
Age ---> Innovativeness	.100 (p>.05)
Gender ---> Innovativeness	.081 (p>.05)
Education ---> Innovativeness	.024 (p>.05)
Tenure ---> Innovativeness	.056 (p>.05)
Industry presence ---> Innovativeness	.075 (p>.05)
No. of employees ---> Innovativeness	.161 (p>.05)
Knowledge sharing practices ---> Innovativeness	.269 (p<.05)
Knowledge availability ---> Innovativeness	.356 (p<.001)

Table 5. Summarised results: final structural model coefficients

Path	Standardized regression estimate (significance)	Squared multiple correlation
Knowledge sharing practices ---> Innovativeness	.338 (p<.001)	.373
Knowledge availability ---> Innovativeness	.494 (p<.001)	